

A CONCEPT IN MODERN LINGUISTICS.

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Annotation: *Concept - a term used to describe the mental resources and mental units of the human mind, as well as information that reflects his experience, knowledge; memory, mental words, and the active unit of the brain are the conceptual system of worldviews reflected in the human psychology, that is, information about a person's perceptions, thoughts, assumptions, and knowledge about world objects. This article discusses the concept in modern linguistics.*

Key words and phrases: *concept, conceptual linguistics, cognitive process, categorization, conceptualization, cognitive model, conceptology.*

Nowadays, the notion of "concept" is becoming an active term not only in cognitive linguistics, but also in many areas related to human speech activity. This, of course, is explained by the growing ties between the fields of modern linguistics. Each of these areas treats the concept as a term that expresses its notions. The question of what the concept, which has become "own" in a number of disciplines, actually means, and what are its specific features in the status of a term, requires a serious approach to the subject. The author of the book "Cognitive Linguistics" Sh. Safarov says: "These questions have not yet been fully answered and are doubtful. There are, of course, reasons for suspicion. First of all, it should not be forgotten that the notion of "concept" is a very abstract phenomenon, the "mental structure" at its core is an imaginary structure that is formed in the process of mental perception, rather than having any material appearance. In addition, the term "concept" goes hand in hand with other mental phenomena, such as "notion", "meaning", "content", and the problem of defining their relationship, distinguishing their distinctive features.

There are different interpretations of the term concept in cognitive research. The concept, which initially appeared in the mind as an image, develops during human activity and expands its semantic scope, as a unit of information structure, it reflects the knowledge, experience, skills and abilities of man about objective reality in his life. Some scholars link the concept to practical philosophy, while others to the national-cultural experience of the speakers. Some scholars interpret the concept as a phrase, while others describe it as a view of the world, a part of it, a national image (idea, symbol), which is complicated by the features of individual imagination.

Today, the need for linguistics to collaborate with cognitive fields such as logic, psychology, and cognitive theory is growing. This collaboration, on the one hand,

introduced linguistics into the field of cognitology, which deals with the problems of human thought, and, on the other hand, enriched linguistics itself with another new field - cognitive linguistics. In linguistics, issues such as the cognitive approach to language and thinking, the meaning of words, the problems of its relationship, the formation of various structures of knowledge through categorization and conceptualization and their expression in language are developing. Conceptualization processes are an example of activity that is an integral part of cognition. They go hand in hand in the mind, but their goals and results are different. The process of conceptualization is aimed at separating the semantic units of the mental level, which are the results of practical experience in human cognitive activity. Conceptualization is the understanding of the transmitted information, the imaginary systematization of objects and events that lead to the formation of certain ideas about the world in the form of concepts. The process of categorization in language is aimed at combining similar phenomena in one or another relationship into larger concepts, categories. However, categorization as a process of cognition is the process of imaginatively attributing an object or event to a particular category.

In modern science, several terms have been proposed to mean a combination of cognition, thinking, and linguistic processes: lingvoculturema, concept, and etc. In my opinion, the most appropriate is concept. The concept reflects perceptions of the universe and realizes it through linguistic means. A concept is an imaginary image of a material or ideal object that is directly related to a language symbol that corresponds directly to the mind. Using the concept, the content of the concept is called, the idea is expressed.

Concept (lot.conceptual: meaning, content, notion) - a term used to describe the mental resources and mental units of the human mind, as well as information that reflects his experience, knowledge; memory, mental words, and the active unit of the brain are the conceptual system of worldviews reflected in the human psychology, that is, information about a person's perceptions, thoughts, assumptions, and knowledge about world objects. The value expressed in all linguistic units has a conceptual nature, because it represents the idea of the value of this or that object's reality. The concept is often considered as a part of the scheme "object - intuition - perception - imagination - concept". A. Vebiskaya describes the concept as an object that is in the "ideal" world and reflects a certain cultural-defined perception of man in the world of reality. Other researchers have linked the concept to a notion that is, a "human concept" - a simple concept of consciousness. Thus, the concept is understood as a unit of the simple view underlying the linguistic landscape of the universe. However, most scientists understand the concept as a syncretic unit of thinking, a much broader mental image. At the same time, they emphasize the integrity of the concept and the probable nature of its structure as specific aspects of the concept.

The concept can be studied from different perspectives. When defining a concept, it is based on the specific purpose of the research. By concept we mean mental unity, a unity of thought in which the knowledge of the object of reality is realized through linguistic means and has a national identity. In linguistics, there is a lack of distinction between the terms concept and notion. According to the internal form of the word, the words concept and notion are the same: the concept is derived from Latin, and conceptus means "concept".

However, they need to be clearly differentiated, because although these terms are systematic, they do not have the same meaning. A notion is a collection of knowledge about the existing features, while a concept is a national-spiritual set of all the knowledge about the given object, which is a set of language tools. The meaning of a word is a means of expressing a concept in language and speech. From birth, man interacts with the objective being that surrounds him: gradually perceives, studies, compares and summarizes the objects and events in nature and society, remembers what they consider necessary by processing the collected information. Evaluates the results of their activities through language.

The concept is the basis of the image and is formed on the basis of the experience of personal feelings. It moves through the stages of abstraction as an image that appears in the human mind. The original content is complicated by additional information, that is, it is enriched by logical symbols. As the level of abstraction increases, the concept evolves from an emotional image to an intellectual image. However, the desired concept should be explained by example. Evidence for a concept is evidence of the nature of the image, the sum of which in the conceptual field forms the conceptsphere. The meaning of a word is cognitive: it consists of semantics that represent certain cognitive features that make up the conceptual content of speech. According to DS Likhachev, the concept should be connected with the word not with the sum of all its meanings, but with one of its main meanings. All the differences between the meaning and the concept are due to the fact that it connects its existence with the sign. In this way, the concept interacts with the meaning of the word, but is not equal to it. The concept is broader and richer than the lexical meaning of the word, because the formation of the concept involves the whole experience of man in the process of learning about the world around him.

In conclusion, the concept is a very complex notion and it does not arise spontaneously. This phenomenon, which occurs during the process of moving from the mind in the form of an image to speech, is formed due to the fact that a person's perception of reality, in other words, gradually develops and improves. That is why the concept, which has passed through the human mind and proved on the basis of life experiences, has a place in the vocabulary of the individual.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. N.N.Boldirev "Cognitive semantics" Tambov 2000
2. Sh.Safarov "Cognitive linguistics" Sangzor, 2003
3. Sh.Safarov "Pragmalinguistics" Tashkent, 2008.
4. Sh.Safarov "Semantics" Tashkent, 2013.
5. Sh.Safarov "Language theory and lingvomethodology" Tashkent, 2015.
6. Vejbitskaya A. "Semantic universals and text descriptions" M., 1999.
7. Vejbitskaya A. "Language. Culture. Recognition", 1997.
8. Vensov A.B., Kasevich V.B. "Проблемы восприятия речи", 1994.

9. Vorkachev S.G. "Лингвокультурология, языковая личность, концерт: становление антропосентрической парадигмы // Филологические науки". 2001.